

Quick Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Quick Ratio using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the Quick Ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the Quick Ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Quick Ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 50 journal publications regarding the Quick Ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the Quick Ratio are divided into 7 clusters and 71 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 6 effects around the Quick Ratio. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around Quick Ratio, so that future researchers can find out research gaps about Quick Ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around Quick Ratio that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can be a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Quick Ratio; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

In the banking context, the quick ratio is an important tool to measure a bank's liquidity and its ability to meet obligations that are due in the short term. The quick ratio provides an overview of the extent to which the bank can pay these obligations using the most liquid assets, such as cash and cash equivalents, securities that are easy to sell, and customer bills that mature in a short time. The use of quick ratios in banking currently includes several things: first, evaluating liquidity. Banks use the quick ratio incorrectly one metric to evaluate their level of liquidity. By having a high quick ratio, banks have more ability to meet their short-term obligations and face urgent financial needs. Second, risk analysis. Quick ratio also helps in analyzing credit risk. Banks need to ensure that they have enough liquid assets to cover the possibility of customers' inability to pay their credit. A low quick ratio can be an indication of potential liquidity problems and higher credit risk. Third, making financing decisions. Quick ratios are also used in making financing decisions by banks. Moment evaluating credit applications from customers, banks will look at the company's quick ratio to assess the company's ability to repay loans in the short term.

Several previous studies have been conducted to analyze the use of quick ratios in the banking industry. Several important findings are revealed in The research is: first research, regarding its relationship with liquidity. Several studies show that a high quick ratio indicates a better level of liquidity, which means the bank has more liquid assets that can be quickly used to meet short-term obligations. Second research, there is research that explores the relationship between the quick ratio and the risk of bankruptcy in financial institutions. The

results of this research vary, but some studies show that a low quick ratio can increase the likelihood of bankruptcy, because banks may have difficulty meeting short-term obligations if they do not have sufficient liquid assets. The third research, comparison between banks. Quick ratios can also be used to compare financial performance between banks different. This research provides insight into the relative strength and financial stability of banks in the face of market changes and difficult financial situations.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around Quick Ratio by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) Library Research studies to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around the Quick Ratio, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research around the Quick Ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around the Quick Ratio which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that it can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

Quick Ratio is one of the financial ratios used in banking financial analysis to assess a bank's ability to fulfill its financial obligations in the short term. This ratio is also known as Acid-Test Ratio. Quick The ratio measures a bank's ability to pay off its short-term obligations without having to rely on selling inventory or assets that are difficult to liquidate such as fixed assets. This ratio is calculated by comparing the most liquid current assets (such as cash, checking accounts, and short-term investments) with short-term liabilities (such as short-term loans, accounts payable, and salaries owed). The Quick Ratio formula is: $\text{Quick Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets} - \text{Inventory}}{\text{Short Term Liabilities}}$. Current assets in this formula do not include inventory because inventory tends to be difficult to convert quickly into cash. By removing inventory from the calculation, the Quick Ratio provides a more conservative picture of a bank's ability to meet its financial obligations in the short term. As a general rule, the higher the Quick Ratio, the better the bank's financial position in facing its short-term obligations. A high Quick Ratio indicates that the bank has a greater ability to pay its short-term obligations without having to rely on resources that are difficult to disburse.

Bibliometric studies are quantitative analyzes used to analyze scientific publications and literature in a particular research field. This method utilizes bibliographic data, such as references, citations, and metadata, to identify trends, patterns, and relationships between existing scientific works. VOSviewer is one of the software tools frequently used in bibliometric studies. This tool is specifically designed to visualize and analyze bibliometric data. In the context of bibliometric studies, VOSviewer is used to analyze reference networks and relationships between scientific publications. By using VOSviewer, researchers can carry out clustering analysis, co-citation analysis, and keyword analysis (Dubyna et al., 2022). Clustering identifies groups of related publications based on similar citation patterns. Co-citation analysis reveals relationships between publications based on references that frequently appear together. Keyword analysis allows researchers to identify the most commonly used keywords in a particular literature. VOSviewer provides interactive and intuitive visualizations, such as cluster maps, co-citation networks, and keyword maps. This visualization helps researchers understand structures and trends in the scientific literature, identify groups of related studies, and see changes over time. In bibliometric studies, VOSviewer has been used in

various research fields, including social sciences, natural sciences, computer science, and others. This tool helps researchers explore scientific literature, identify academic collaborations, and extract new insights from bibliometric data (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a systematic process for collecting, evaluating, and synthesizing research that is relevant and related to a particular research topic. The primary goal of a Library Research is to gain a comprehensive understanding of what is known about the topic, identify gaps in knowledge that may exist, and provide a solid theoretical basis for the research being conducted. Library Research studies involve searching and collecting relevant literature, whether in the form of journal articles, books, theses, research reports, or other sources of information. Once the literature is collected, the researcher then evaluates and critically analyzes each source to identify the main findings, methodology used, emerging findings, and the contribution of the research to understanding the topic (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is Quick Ratio. The type of data used is data secondary. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on Quick Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Tool Data analysis using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key " Quick Ratio " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around Quick Ratio using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on year of publication; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around Quick Ratio using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Quick Ratio using a Library Research study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications regarding Quick Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 50 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2005 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding the Quick Ratio by year

Year	Amount	Year	Amount	Year	Amount
	Publication		Publication		Publication
2005	1	2014	2	2019	2

2006	1	2015	4	2020	3
2009	1	2016	6	2021	3
2010	1	2017	4	2022	2
2012	2	2018	11	2023	2
2013	5				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Mapping Research Topics around Quick Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using VOSviewer Bibliometric Studies

Article search results in the Perish/Harzing software are exported in format

RIS (Research Information Systems), then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around the Quick Ratio.

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

The VOSViewer software visualization regarding the research development map regarding Quick Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, there are 7 clusters and 71 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1 consists of 15 topic items, namely: Indonesian bank, book value, debt, decision, der, effect, equity ratio, murabaha financing, good, Islamic bank, murabaha financing, price, quarterly financial statement, study, variable.
- Cluster 2 consists of 14 topic items, namely: cash ratio, current ratio, data, December, form, influence, liquidity, multiple linear regression analysis, central bank debt payments, productive financing, quick ratio and cash ratio, sampling technique, secondary data, sharia commercial bank.
- Cluster 3 consists of 13 topic items, namely: adequacy ratio, analysis of the influence of the quick ratio, bopo, car, dividend payout ratio, equity, Indonesia, the influence of the capital adequacy ratio, financial performance

on the profitability of Bank Syariah Mandiri Indonesia, ratio, return, roe, significant effect.

- Cluster 4 consists of 11 topic items, namely: assets, Islamic State Bank of Indonesia, deposit ratio, FDR, financing, net profit margin, NPM, influence of financing, influence of quick ratio, ROA, significant on returns.
- Cluster 5 consists of 9 topic items, namely: Bank Muamalat Indonesia, banking ratio, capital adequacy ratio, capital ratio, concern, loan, net interest margin, influence of current ratio, banking companies.
- Cluster 6 consists of 8 topic items, namely: banks, deposits, gross profit margin, liquidity gap and non-performing loans, Persero, PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia, Indonesian Bank Standards, studies on conventional commercial banks.
- Cluster 7 consists of 1 topic item, namely: ipr.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Influence of the Quick Ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 6 influences of the Quick Ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, Return On Assets/ROA. The effect of the quick ratio on ROA in banking can vary depending on economic conditions, company strategy and other factors. However, in general, a high quick ratio tends to have a positive influence on ROA. The following are several reasons why a high quick ratio can have a positive impact on banking ROA: (1) Higher liquidity: Quick A high ratio indicates that the company has good liquidity, meaning they have enough liquid assets to meet their short-term obligations. In a banking context, this could mean companies have a better ability to lend money to customers and generate interest or other income on the assets they own. High liquidity can also help companies face emergency situations or urgent funding needs. (2) Ability to overcome credit risk: A high quick ratio also shows the company's ability to overcome credit risk. In the banking business, credit risk is an important factor that needs to be managed well. By having a high quick ratio, the company has more liquid assets that can be used to cover the possible risk of default from borrowers. This can help companies minimize losses that may arise due to misuse of credit or bad credit. (3) Customer trust: A high quick ratio can build customer and investor trust. Customers and investors tend to have more confidence in companies that have strong liquidity, because this shows that the company can fulfill their financial obligations smoothly. This high level of trust can encourage banking business growth, increase transaction volume, and ultimately increase ROA.

Second, Return On Equity /ROE. The influence of the quick ratio on ROE in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Liquidity and Risk: The quick ratio provides an overview of the company's liquidity and its ability to meet short-term obligations. The higher the quick ratio, the more liquid the company and the higher the probability of meeting short-term obligations. In the banking industry, having a high quick ratio can help reduce liquidity risk, so it can have a positive impact on ROE. (2) Operational Efficiency: A healthy quick ratio can show that the company has good cash management and efficiency in managing its assets. In banking, efficient management in asset management and liquidity can increase net income, which in turn can increase ROE. (3) Funding Sources: A low quick ratio may indicate that the company is dependent on short-term funding sources, such as short-term loans. Short-term loans usually have higher costs compared to long-term funding. Thus, depending on expensive short-term funding sources can reduce the net income available to shareholders, potentially negatively affecting ROE.

Third, productive financing. The influence of the quick ratio on productive financing in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Liquidity: The quick ratio provides an idea of how liquid the bank is in meeting short-term obligations. The higher the quick ratio, the more liquid assets available to finance the bank's operational and productive activities. In this case, a high quick ratio can provide greater flexibility for banks in providing productive financing to their customers. (2) Credit Risk: The quick ratio can also be used as an indicator of credit risk in productive financing. Banks that have a low quick ratio indicate limited liquidity, which can cause difficulties in meeting credit requests from potentially productive customers. This risk can hamper the bank's ability to provide productive financing effectively. (3) Customer Trust: A high quick ratio can give customers confidence regarding the bank's ability to provide productive financing. Customers tend to have more confidence in banks that have adequate liquidity capabilities to meet their credit requests. This customer trust can encourage the growth of productive financing, because customers will be more likely to apply for credit from banks that are considered to have sufficient liquidity. (4) Growth and Expansion: A high quick ratio can enable banks to allocate more funds for productive financing. By having adequate liquidity, banks can meet higher credit demands from customers who want to develop their businesses or expand their business. This productive financing can encourage economic growth and help increase bank income through interest and profits from this financing.

Fourth, Murabahah financing. The effect of the quick ratio on Murabahah financing in banking can vary depending on several factors. The following are several possible influences that could occur: (1) Ease of financing: If the banking quick ratio is high, this means that the company has good liquidity and is able to meet short-term obligations with liquid current assets. In this case, banks can more easily provide Murabahah financing to customers, because they have sufficient liquidity to carry out such transactions. (2) Credit risk: A low quick ratio indicates an unfavorable level of liquidity, which can cause difficulties in meeting short-term obligations. In this case, banks may be more careful in providing Murabahah financing, as there is a higher risk associated with refunds by customers. (3) Bank policy considerations: The effect of the quick ratio on Murabahah financing can also be influenced by the bank's internal policies. Each bank has different policies in terms of financing requirements and risk tolerance. Some banks may be more inclined to provide Murabahah financing even if the quick ratio is low, while others may be more conservative and require a high quick ratio before providing financing.

Fifth, return on assets. The effect of the quick ratio on return on assets in banking can vary depending on various factors, including business strategy, market conditions, and the overall economic environment. In general, there are several possible effects that can occur: (1) Sufficient liquidity: If quick The banking ratio is quite high, meaning the company has strong liquidity and can meet short-term obligations easily. This can provide confidence to creditors and investors, which can have a positive impact on the company's reputation. In the long term, a good reputation can help banks attract new customers and obtain cheaper funds, thereby increasing returns on assets. (2) Potential for lower returns: An increase in the quick ratio may also indicate that the company is choosing to hold more liquid assets, such as cash, rather than allocating them to investments that have the potential to generate higher returns. In this case, the return on assets may be lower due to less productive assets. (3) Effect on cost of capital: A low quick ratio may indicate that the company is facing difficulties in meeting its short-term obligations quickly. This can increase the company's risk and encourage creditors

to increase capital costs, such as loan interest rates. An increase in the cost of capital can reduce the return on banking assets. (4) Influence on operational efficiency: A balanced and optimal quick ratio can help companies manage liquidity risk well. In these conditions, companies can focus more on operational efficiency and make better use of assets to generate revenue. Thus, the right quick ratio can support higher returns on assets.

Sixth, stock returns. The effect of the quick ratio on stock returns in banking can vary depending on several factors. The following are several considerations that need to be taken into account: (1) Liquidity: A high quick ratio indicates that the bank has a better ability to meet its short-term obligations. This could mean that banks have higher liquidity and can overcome difficult financial situations. This can provide confidence to investors, which in turn can have a positive impact on stock returns.

(2) Investor confidence: Financial ratios, including the quick ratio, are used by investors as indicators to evaluate a company's financial performance. If the banking quick ratio shows a positive trend over time, investors may feel more confident and interested in investing in banking shares. This can affect demand for shares and potentially increase stock returns.

(3) Risk: A low quick ratio can indicate that banks have higher liquidity risk, meaning they may have difficulty meeting short-term obligations in the event of a difficult financial situation. This can affect investors' perceptions of the risks associated with these banking shares and can have a negative impact on stock returns. (4) Banking industry: The effect of the quick ratio on stock returns is also influenced by conditions and trends in the banking industry overall. If the banking industry is experiencing good performance, a high quick ratio at a bank may be considered a competitive advantage and can have a positive impact on stock returns.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding quick ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2005 to 2023 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 50 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding quick ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 7 clusters and 71 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 15 topics, cluster 2 consists of 14 topics, cluster 3 consists of 13 topics, cluster 4 consists of 11 topics, cluster 5 consists of 9 topics, cluster 6 consists of 8 topics, and cluster 7 consists of 1 topic. Third, based on the mapping of the Library Research study, there are 6 topics related to the influence of the quick ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, productive financing, Murabahah financing, return on assets, and return on shares.

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